

Biogeochemical processes and ecosystem function in changing polar systems and their global impacts (BIOPOLE)

Communications Plan for the BIOPOLE Programme

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1. Background

BIOPOLE is an ambitious £9M collaborative UKRI NC funded project is addressing a fundamental knowledge gap in Earth System functioning – *how polar ecosystems regulate the balance of carbon and nutrients in the world's oceans, driving primary productivity, fisheries, and the global carbon cycle.*

To deliver its research BIOPOLE is operating simultaneously in the Arctic and Antarctic using a range of innovative tools including data mining, laboratory bioassays, fieldwork, and modelling.

BIOPOLE will provide solutions to urgent challenges in Earth system modelling through the inclusion of vital ecosystem processes, thereby improving policy decision-making on climate and fisheries.

BIOPOLE uses a multidisciplinary, internationally collaborative, and highly coordinated approach which maximises our research power and minimises our carbon footprint. It unites five UKRI-NERC Research Centres – UKCEH, BGS, CPOM, NOC and BAS and a range of international Science Partners and Strategic Partners (the 'BIOPOLE Community'). It capitalises on the UK's world-leading capability and infrastructure in ocean and high-latitude research, including cutting-edge land-based facilities, the new state-of-the-art polar research vessel, and innovative autonomous instrumentation.

BIOPOLE's legacy will be the first assessment of the global impact of polar ecosystems on the chemical balance of the oceans, primary productivity, fish stocks, and the global carbon cycle; technologically novel approaches to delivering large-scale marine science; and strong collaborative partnerships between UK NC-funded institutes and leading international groups and.

2. Aim and objectives

The aim of this communications plan is to provide BIOPOLE Project Members and the media departments of our UKRI-NERC Research Centres (BAS, BGS, CPOM, and NOC, and UKCEH) with a framework for disseminating the progress, results, and impacts of the BIOPOLE Programme. Objectives include:

- Building awareness of the project among a target audience, such as potential end users
- Securing the commitment of a target group of stakeholders to the project aims, e.g., new funders
- Influencing specific policies or policymakers on key aspects
- Encouraging participation from groups or organisations

Specific examples include:

- Enabling two-way dialogue between BIOPOLE **Project Members** and **NC-funded institutes** (including the five BIOPOLE institutes, BAS, BGS, CEH, CPOM, NOC) and the science-user community (primarily UK)
- Enabling two-way dialogue between BIOPOLE [Project Members](#), [Science Partners](#), and [Strategic Partners](#) (collectively referred to as the BIOPOLE Community)
- Fostering science communication and wider interactions with the stakeholders beyond the BIOPOLE Community, including **national and international science community** and **UK Higher Education Institutes** on the work of BIOPOLE (including activities, such as fieldwork and the achievement of major milestones and deliverables)
- Delivering synthesised findings to the key **UK government departments** to support UK obligations under the Antarctic Treaty and engagement with the Arctic Council

- Further informing decision-making by the **Convention for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources** (CCAMLR) and the **Arctic Council**, and supporting national and inter-governmental climate change negotiations and UK geopolitical influence via the UK Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO, including the Polar Regions Department)
- Ensuring BIOPOLE outputs contribute to **global ocean ecosystem analyses and assessments**, including Earth System Models (ESMs), and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), World Ocean Atlas (WOA)
- Ensuring BIOPOLE outputs contribute to the **United Nations** (UN) Sustainability Goals and UN 'specialised agencies', 'related organisations', and 'inter-agency mechanisms' supporting sustainable ocean governance, including The Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), UN Climate Change, and UN Oceans

3. Implementation plan

- Identify key milestones to plan a calendar of key programme activities
- Regular evaluation reports and analysis of previous digital BIOPOLE content to inform future campaigns
- Review BIOPOLE brand and templates for staff
- Press releases at key milestones and publications
- Press releases or news stories will be compiled as appropriate, with the assistance of Centres' media teams, as well as NERC's press team as required
- BIOPOLE management to contact responsible individuals in advance of fieldwork/key milestones/deliverables to gather and collaboratively prepare information to be communicated
- The PAB will be consulted for best practice and further opportunities for engagement
- A report on impacts will be made as an agenda item in our annual BIOPOLE meetings and collate our impacts over the course of the programme as part of our final report

4. Desired outcome/Evaluation

- Metrics of various communication tools (see 'Table 2: List of Communication Tools and Monitoring Methods') will be regularly collated to determine the effectiveness of BIOPOLE postings and how widely BIOPOLE science is being picked up by national and international media. The external impact will be monitored.
- Feedback will be requested from outreach talks and presentations to assess whether BIOPOLE science is being communicated in a clear and engaging way and to make improvements where necessary.

5. Key messages

A set of key messages (and supporting messages) are outlined below. These are designed to communicate:

- What BIOPOLE is
- Why the research done under BIOPOLE is important
- What challenges in the polar regions we are addressing
- What solutions we are aiming to deliver (impacts)

The messages reflect the goal and objectives of the programme as well as the approach it is taking to deliver them. The messages can be tailored for communicating with different audiences/stakeholder groups (e.g., public, scientists and science organisations, policy makers) and will be updated as the programme progresses.

The 5 key messages can be used on their own. If further detail is needed, the supporting messages (or part thereof) can be added.

5.1 Top-line messages

{= extra detail if needed}

Key message 1:

BIOPOLE is developing new insights into **polar ecosystem processes**, which are highly sensitive to climate change, and exploring their **global impacts** under scenarios of future climate change [*Novelty, tag line*].

Key message 2:

BIOPOLE is investigating how Arctic and Antarctic (polar) ecosystems regulate the balance of carbon and nutrients in the polar and global oceans, driving primary productivity, fisheries production, and the global carbon cycle [*Overarching Goal*].

Supporting messages

- The climate-sensitive polar regions are integral to the Earth system, interacting with the rest of the world via the oceans, atmosphere, and ecological and social systems.
- A fundamental knowledge gap in Earth System functioning is the mechanisms and extent to which the polar regions and their unique ecosystems influence the balance of carbon and nutrients in the world's oceans or contribute to the cycling of carbon through the biosphere
- These polar processes are undoubtedly vital to maintaining a healthy global ocean, its ability to sustain life, support economies [e.g., fisheries and tourism], and regulate our climate but at the same time they are under threat from climate change. Understanding their response to future climate change is therefore an urgent global priority [*Challenges, Rationale*]

Key Message 3:

To achieve this goal, our research is focussed on three key questions:

1. What are the key sources and flows of nutrients (primarily nitrogen and phosphorous) from glaciers, rivers, sea ice, and ocean upwelling processes into the polar oceans? [*Objective, Work Package 1 'Inputs'*]

2. How do polar marine ecosystems {including microorganisms and small zooplankton called copepods} process carbon and nutrients, influencing their balance {i.e., the Redfield Ratio C:N:P} in the polar oceans and the amount of carbon that is sequestered (stored) into the deep ocean? [*Objective, Work Package 2 'Processes'*]

3. How are carbon and nutrients exported to the rest of the world's oceans and what are their impacts on {the balance of oceanic elements C, N and P, } marine primary productivity and fisheries in the mid latitudes, and the {storage and} cycling of carbon through our biosphere? [*Objective, Work Package 3 'Impacts'*]

We are also determining the climate sensitivity of all these aspects and their response to future climate change scenarios at the polar and global levels. [*Objective, Work Packages 1-3*]

Key message 4:

By quantifying these aspects, we will be able to predict with greater certainty how global marine primary productivity (which fuels almost all animal life in the oceans), fisheries, and climate regulation may be affected by future global change. This will allow policy makers to prepare for and adapt to the consequences of climate change [*Objective, Work Package 4, Solutions*]

Supporting messages

- We will provide new insights into the export of nutrients from the polar regions and its role in the chemical balance of the oceans. We will quantify this export, its climate sensitivity, and its impact on future primary productivity and fisheries production.
- We will inject much needed information on polar biology and ecosystem processes into an Earth System Model of the carbon cycle {MEDUSA}, providing more robust projections of future changes in the Earth system and its response to anthropogenic emissions.
- Our findings will provide policy makers with vital information to support regional marine conservation and fisheries management decisions and global climate mitigation and adaptation strategies.

Key message 5:

To answer these big questions, we are collaborating with leading UK science institutes and international partners, using a multidisciplinary approach and state-of-the-art polar research infrastructure.

Supporting messages

- Our ambitious programme is using the capabilities and state-of-the-art NERC infrastructure of our 5 UK NERC research centres, together with those of our national and international partners. This approach maximises our research power and minimises our carbon footprint.

- Our programme unites physical scientists, biogeochemists, ecologists, fisheries scientist, and modellers who are integrating data from observations and analyses into models of carbon and nutrient flows.
- We are making extensive use of existing data that has already been collected in the polar regions.
- We are collecting new field data from land, rivers, sea ice, and seas in both the Arctic and Antarctic, using small boats, ships {including the *RRS Sir David Attenborough*}, and range of autonomous instruments including moorings and gliders.
- We are conducting bioassays to determine the sensitivity of key plankton species {phytoplankton and copepods} to climate change and the consequences to ocean biogeochemistry
- We are using a range of modelling approaches {lagrangian, idealised, fish biomass, regional and global modelling} to investigate the flows of carbon and nutrients from the polar regions to the global ocean, and understand their impacts on marine productivity, fisheries, and climate regulation now and into the future.

5.2 Story House for communicating with the media
(NOTE open in desktop app for correct formatting)

Answering these big questions on **Polar Ecosystems and their Global Impacts** is really important...

Societal solutions
It will improve our ability to predict the future health of our ocean by providing better estimates of fisheries production and its ability to regulate our climate. This will improve policy decision-making to better prepare for and adapt to the consequence of changing world

Roof: Overarching goal

BIOPOLE is addressing a major unknown in the way our Earth functions - how polar ecosystems (in the Arctic and Antarctic) regulate the balance of carbon and nutrients in the world's oceans to keep them healthy and productive. We are addressing this through three key, inter-linked questions:

Support structures: Answering these big questions requires the ambitious, multidisciplinary, and highly strategic approach of BIOPOLE. To deliver our research we are operating simultaneously in both polar regions, uniting scientists from a range of disciplines (physics, biogeochemistry and ecology), and using innovative tools including data mining, laboratory bioassays, fieldwork campaigns, and computer modelling. This approach maximises our research power and minimises our carbon footprint, allowing us to address this globally important issue.

The version of key messages outlined in the Storyhouse (Figure 5.2) can be used to prepare for talking to the media, general public etc. Each of these Storyhouse elements can be used alone, or together, to reinforce messages about the BIOPOLE programme. *TIPS: Greg Foot from the BBC has an excellent course on communicating science (to media and stakeholders) with videos and downloadable PDFs . See more at <http://www.bit.ly/TalkingScienceYouTu...>*

5.3. Quotes

- 'BIOPOLE is undertaking a truly ambitious programme of research in both polar regions. Our aim is to understand the role that both poles play in determining the chemical balance of the oceans. It is this balance that facilitates the productivity of all marine life and their role in storing carbon and regulating climate. This research will include deployment of advanced autonomous instruments capable of gathering data in critical but otherwise inaccessible parts of the polar oceans. It will also make use of one of world's most advanced research vessels, including the *RRS Sir David Attenborough*'. Prof Geraint Tarling (BAS), Principal Investigator, BIOPOLE.

5.4 About the programme

- BIOPOLE is a £9M 5-year multidisciplinary research programme (2022-27) funded by the National Capability Science Multi-Centre award scheme of the United Kingdom's Natural Environment Research Council (NERC, part of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)). The scheme is designed to enable a more ambitious, integrated approach to research challenges that require large-scale, long-timeline insights and more than any one National Capability (NC) provider can deliver alone. The scheme also aims to bring skill sets and expertise together, to meet national science needs through more coherent and resilient delivery across NC providers and to increase NC science returns by generating new science opportunities that leverage additional benefits via other funding streams. BIOPOLE is made up of five UK National Capability providers (in alphabetical order): British Antarctic Survey (BAS), British Geological Survey (BGS), Centre for Polar Observation and Modelling (CPOM), National Oceanography Centre (NOC), and UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (UKCEH). BIOPOLE is led by the BAS and Prof Geraint Tarling is the Principal Investigator.

6. Key audiences and channels of communication

Our key audiences and channels of communication are summarised in Table 1. Communication tools and monitoring methods are shown in Table 2.

7. Visual identity and resources

We have generated a series of resources to aid the communication of the programme. To raise awareness about BIOPOLE, its research and results, we need to maintain a strong identity. This will provide consistency in the communication and help attract audience attention. To this end we have created a range of branding resources to be used by BIOPOLE Project Members, Science Partners, and Strategic Partners. This visual identity has also been imbedded into our websites, social media channels and newsletter.

7.1. Websites

We have created a dedicated BIOPOLE website at www.biopole.ac.uk, which is maintained and updated by Work Package 4. A further dedicated website regarding our status as an endorsed BIOPOLE Project (Polar Ecosystems, Polar Impacts, BIOPOLE) is on the [UN Ocean Decade website](#). This is also maintained by Work Package 4.

7.2. Social media channels

We have dedicated Twitter and Facebook accounts. We encourage inclusion of our Project Collaborators (Science Partners and Strategic Partners) account handles in all posts. We continue to identify and use popular hashtags (e.g., #ClimateAction, #ClimateChange, #PolarRegions), which are regularly updated. These resources are available on the BIOPOLE Shared drive ([Popular social media handles and hashtags](#)) and our BIOPOLE Website.

7.3. Seasonal newsletter

We develop a seasonal newsletter. This, together with our website, is our primary mode of communication with the BIOPOLE Community to keep them up to date with news, events and the latest research findings. This newsletter is accessible via email lists (maintained by Work Package 4) and is also posted on our websites.

7.4. Logo and tagline

The BIOPOLE logo has been created by Ralph Design Ltd. The logo contains our tag line '**Polar Ecosystems, Global Impacts**'. It is an important element of the programme as the full name – *BIOPOLE - Biogeochemical processes and ecosystem function in changing polar systems and their global impacts* may not resonate with the general public. A logo has also been created for our Project Collaborators, to symbolise their involvement in the programme (using the tag line Science Partners, Strategic Partners). The logos, and details on the exact colours used, can be found in our visual identity toolkit.

7.5. Visual identity toolkit

The visual identity toolkit is available on the BIOPOLE Shared Drive and the BIOPOLE Website (under Resources). As the project progresses other relevant materials will be added to the toolkit.

7.5.1 Templates

We have created a set of templates including;

- Word document (to serve as a report format or one page documents)

- PowerPoint templates for individual science presentations and posters
- Social media banner templates (in PPT format)

7.5.2 General presentation and poster for scientific events

We have created general presentation and poster (in PPT format) that give an overview of the project objectives, structure and latest results. These can be used by Project Members at internal and external meetings. These will be updated quarterly (and as necessary based on events organised by the programme or in external conferences, workshops, seminars etc). These resources can be adapted by Project Members to suit their audience.

7.5.3 Banner

We have commissioned a 2m x 80cm roll up banner, summarising the programme, to be used by Project Members at public engagement events.

7.5.4 Graphics

We have commissioned a graphic capturing BIOPOLE concept and the 3 key research questions we are addressing. The individual silhouettes that comprise the graphic are also available separately. We have also commissioned graphics that capture the research 'tools' employed by the programme including, field work, data mining, biogeochemical analyses, modelling and dissemination. All of these graphics can be used by Project Members and Collaborators and can be found on the BIOPOLE Shared Drive.

7.5.5 Videos

We are in the process of developing a series of videos capturing the work of the programme. These will also be available on the BIOPOLE website and Shared Drive.

- Animation video (Lead Clara Manno)
- Live action (Lead TBT)
 - Both capturing aspects of
 - Talking heads/voice over on the challenge, goals, work packages, tools, solutions, international collaborations, dissemination
 - Data mining
 - Bioassays (copepod respiration experiments, nutrient analyses)
 - Fieldwork (land based, small boats, rivers, glaciers, marine fieldwork including RRS Sir David Attenborough and collaborator vessels, autonomous platforms)
 - Modelling
 - Policy impacts

8. Risks

- Communication with indigenous peoples - It is important that aspects of communications are made accessible to Inuit communities and any impact on their way of life is considered. Many of our Project Partners have established collaborations with members of these communities,

and considerable experience in this area to draw upon. The Partnering with Indigenous Peoples: Experiences and Practices prepared by the UN will be used as a guidance document linked here: [Partnering with Indigenous Peoples: \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/).

- Uncertainty – disassociating scientific theory from opinion when speaking about uncertainty to public and media
- Conflicting messages

Table 1: Key audiences and channels

Audience	Why and what	Channels	Delivered by
Key UK government departments (the UK Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, Department of Energy and Climate Change (under DSIT), and the Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office)	Deliver synthesised findings to the key UK government departments to support UK obligations under the Antarctic Treaty and engagement with the Arctic Council	Through stakeholder fora White papers Target the All-Party Parliamentary Group for the Polar Regions	BIOPOLE Members
Policy makers	Further inform decision-making by the Convention for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources (CCAMLR) and support national and inter-governmental climate change negotiations and UK geopolitical influence	Via membership and events attendance Reports Publications Factsheets Policy briefs Invitation to project meetings	BIOPOLE Members BIOPOLE Management team
Science community	Foster science communication and wider interactions with the national and international science community on BIOPOLE and its work (including activities, such as fieldwork and the achievement of major milestones by the programme)	BIOPOLE website Twitter Facebook BIOPOLE BAS page Conferences Publications Reports Presentations Posters BIOPOLE banner Seasonal newsletter IMBeR Newsletter to target China Press Releases Workshops	BIOPOLE Members
Public and young people	Increase awareness to a wider community of the interconnection of polar ecosystems and the balance of carbon and nutrients in the world's oceans and their effect on global fish stocks and carbon storage, and enable dialog with the project	Science festivals School visits Public science talks Podcasts Web and social media channels: website, Facebook, Twitter Videos Seasonal newsletter	BIOPOLE Members

Internal (Project Members, Programme Advisory Board, Project Partners)	Enable effective communication to maximise collaboration	JiscMail Mailing Lists Meetings Reports Seasonal Newsletter Workshops Web and social media channels: website, Facebook, Twitter	BIOPOLE Members BIOPOLE Management team
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Table 2: Communication tools and monitoring methods

	Communication Tools	Frequency	Monitoring Tools	Metrics	Indicators of Success
Online	BIOPOLE Website https://biopole.ac.uk/	Quarterly	WordPress stats	Number of visitors Number of views Locations by views Engagement Number of posts published Number of file downloads	Constant increase of the number of visitors, views, engagement No decrease observed Posting monthly
	BIOPOLE page on BAS website BIOPOLE - British Antarctic Survey (bas.ac.uk)	Quarterly	WordPress stats		
	Newsletter	Quarterly	Mailchimp analytics	Number of subscribers Number of opens Locations by opens	No unsubscriptions recorded Increasing number of opens
	Mailing Lists	Quarterly	JiscMail statistics	Number of subscribers	Consistent number of subscribers
Social Media	Twitter	Quarterly	Twitter analytics	Number of tweets Number of followers Impressions Engagement	Regular tweets Increase in the number of followers, impressions and engagement
	Facebook	Quarterly		Number of posts Number of followers Post impressions Post reach	Regular posts Increase in the number of followers,

				Post engagement	impressions, reach, and engagement
Media	Press Releases	Annually	Analytics	Number of press releases Engagement	
Events	Conference Participation	Annually	Analytics	Number of presentations/keynotes/posters Number of attendees	1 presentation a month, around 12 per year
	Annual Meeting	Annually	Analytics	Number of attendees, feedback	Positive feedback (survey) from participants and PAB Around 50-60 project members and 30 collaborators attending
	Workshops	Annually	Analytics	Number of workshops Number of attendees	3 per year A target of 20 attendees
	Science Festivals	Annually	Analytics	Number of festivals Number of attendees	2 per year
Publications	Scientific Publications	Annually	Analytics	Number of articles in peer-reviewed journals	35 in the duration of the programme
	Reports	Annually	Analytics	Number of reports Number of downloads (where possible)	Annual reports, halfway report, end of programme report